

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D3.3 Report on CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime v1.0

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
ADAS	Advanced driver-assistance systems
BTP	Block Transfer Protocol
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility / Cooperative awareness message
CAN	Controller Area Network
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems and Services
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle to Everything
D2D	Device to Device
DbW	Drive by Wire
DDS	Data Distribution Service
DSRC	Dedicated Short Range Communication
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FOV	Field of View
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
HPCu	High performance computing unit
IDL	Interface Description Language
IMU	Inertial Motion Unit
ITS-G5	European standard for vehicular communications based on IEEE-1609.x and IEEE-802.11p standards
LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
LTE	Long-Term Evolution (telecommunication)
MAPEM	MAP extended message
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVI	Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure
NR	New Radio
OBU	On Board Unit
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection

PC5	Interface used for direct communication between a vehicle and other devices
PDU	Power Distribution Unit
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
RSU	Road-Side Unit
SoA	State of the Art
SOC	System On Chip
SPATEM	Signal Phase And Timing Extended Message
UE	User Equipment
UHD	Ultra-High Definition
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication
Uu	Interface for cellular communication between device and base station
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR/AR	Virtual Reality / Augmented reality
VRU	Vulnerable road user

1 Executive Summary

The deliverable D3.3 is the result of Task 3.2 and describes a common view on hardware, software and network architectures for required to fulfil different use-case scenarios. This document introduces different partners' plans to develop or improve upon existing architectures based on the knowledge gained during the first year of WP3. The focus is on currently available hardware and software components, current SoA, possible improvements to existing systems, along with a look into network architectures. The subsequent document (D3.4) will show the final architecture and parts of its implementation, based on the experience gained during the use-case trial phase.

This deliverable describes available and planned infrastructure in road, railway, and maritime environments, along with details on specific vehicle architectures (road vehicles, trains, and ferries) and required network functionalities. The term *architecture* refers to systems and component constellations related to a particular unit such as a vehicle, ferry, train, or traffic light intersection, while *infrastructure* will be used to describe components and their constellations beyond these units such as network and communication infrastructure elements, which are necessary to fulfil unit architectures. The goal is to use a common network infrastructure for all involved use-cases, while adapting use-case-relevant architectures as needed, for example, specific hardware (sensors, road equipment etc.) and software.

Certain risks are identified during Task 3.2, the most significant of which is the availability of 3GPP Release 16 and 17 modems. Another challenge is ensuring stable 5G-connectivity during the trials, either due to sources of interference or blocked signal paths. During the test and trial phases, these issues will be further examined, and the found solutions will be reported in D3.4.

2 Introduction

The main objective of this deliverable is to facilitate the development of the necessary infrastructure and architecture for the realization of different use-cases. This section shows how the topics of D3.3 fit in the broader context of the 5G-ROUTES project.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1. Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D3.3 Report on CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime v1.0	<p>Objectives:</p> <p>To develop the relevant infrastructure in vehicles, railways and maritime for the provision of CAM services.</p> <p>To integrate the 5G infrastructure with the innovative technological enablers.</p> <p>To setup and conduct lab trials to verify proper operation of CAM services and reduce ambiguities prior to conducting large-scale trials in the field.</p>	<p>Infrastructure for intersections – Chapter 4</p> <p>Infrastructure for vehicles – Chapter 5</p> <p>Infrastructure for Railways – Chapter 6</p> <p>Infrastructure for Maritime – Chapter 7</p>	The deliverable outcomes are used to identify architecture components towards each use case group implementation.
TASKS			
Task 3.2: Development of CAM infrastructure in vehicles, railways and maritime	<p>This task will address the development of CAM infrastructure in vehicles, roads, railways and in maritime, entailing the 5G CAM technological enablers and innovations to be validated in the trials. In particular, leverage and development the CAM infrastructure for enabling the execution of the use cases in the field trials, including the relevant interfaces to the 5G infrastructure. Most effort would be focused on use case specific application development. The use case applications will be delivered as VNFs compliant with the respective Core and Edge NFVIs, and can leverage the vendors' development, testing and</p>	<p>CAM infrastructure with reference to use-cases – chapters 3 - 7</p> <p>VNFs with the respective Core and Edge NFVIs – section 3.2</p> <p>In-vehicle OBUs, 5G modems, UHD cameras and other sensors – section 3.3 and chapter 5</p> <p>Telemetry operations – section 6.2</p>	N/A

	<p>certification frameworks. In particular:</p> <p>(a) In vehicles: OBUs, vehicular set of sensors for proximity, lane designation, geometry, road conditions, positioning, stability & traction control, lidars, 5G modems, UHD cameras with video streaming capabilities between vehicles, AR-based navigation, digital maps and automated navigation maps, applications for autonomous driving, traffic jam chauffeur, etc. (b) For prosumers and consumers: infotainment and business collaboration applications with VR/AR and 3D capabilities, 5G enabled UEs; (c) For railways: telemetry operation applications, 5G MEC-enabled small cells; (d) For maritime: applications to track and monitor cargo's journey based on 5G IoT location-based sensors, also combined with (b) and 5G small cells; (e) For road infrastructure: AI-based intersection controller system, road side units, intelligent light system, 360o UHD elevated cameras with geolocation tagging.</p>	5G IoT location-based sensors – section 7.2	
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2.2 Linkage to Other Project Outputs

This subsection takes the reports of other work packages into account and shows how this deliverable relates to them in Table 2.

Table 2. Past and future deliverables related to D3.3

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Deliverable Chapter(s)	Contribution and Value of linkage
INPUTS from other deliverables <u>utilised in this report</u>		
D1.1 Use-cases, scenarios, specifications, and target KPIs for 5G and CAM	2, 3	<p>Input: stakeholder overview, 5G network introduction, use-case introduction along with testing facilities and KPIs.</p> <p>In this deliverable: more detailed overview of technologies and infrastructure that will be used by the stakeholders to address the different use-cases.</p>
D1.3 CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies	3, 4	<p>Input: high-level use-case overview, network KPIs, relevant 5G functionalities, 5G deployment plan and readiness in Latvia, Estonia, and Finland.</p>

		In this deliverable: more specific use-case descriptions and infrastructure availability (along with planned changes) of the stakeholders.
D1.5 Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM	3, 4	Input: methodologies and KPIs for cross-border 5G validation for CAM. In this deliverable: descriptions of trials for network-KPI validation.
D1.7 Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results	3.3, 6	Input: general and use-case specific overview of data collection and test strategies. In this deliverable: descriptions of specific equipment that will be used to conduct test trials.
D2.1 5G-ROUTES project architecture, cross domain integration fabric	3, 4.2	Input: uninterrupted services across multiple domains. In this deliverable: chapter 3 (network connectivity) and chapter 7 (maritime vehicles) are relevant in multiple-domain context which are going to be expanded.
D2.3 Network slicing mechanisms for cross border	3.2, 4.1, 4.2, 4.4	Input: network slice negotiation and lifecycle management. In this deliverable: to be utilized for all the use-cases, infrastructure integration.
D2.5 Localization solutions for V2X and IoT use-cases	4.2, 5.1, 5.4	Input: V2X positioning enhancements. In this deliverable: positioning services for V2X and IoT use-cases to be integrated and tested.
D2.7 Tenant web portal for KPI visualization and cloud platform	4.2, 4.3, 4.5, 5.1, 5.2	Input: tenant web portal and how UCs interact with it. In this deliverable: data repositories and cloud integration for use-cases.
D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological Enablers for CAM v1.0	4, 6.1	Input: Enabler integration strategy in the 5G-ROUTES platform. In this deliverable: chapter 3 addresses the CAM Services of UCs that will leverage the functionalities offered by the Enablers.
OUTPUTS from this report utilised by other deliverables		
D3.4 Report on CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime v2.0	3, 4, 5, 6, 7	D3.4 is the direct follow-up deliverable of D3.3, so most chapters are expected to use and/or improve the information about the used infrastructure and solution architectures for the different use-cases.
D3.8 Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness v1.0	3, 5	D3.8 will describe how the work, performed on the vehicles, is integrated with the other network components, and the different components used in the use cases will be tested and verified for trial readiness.

2.3 Infrastructure Development Overview

Table 3 gives an overview of the equipment used in the different 5G-ROUTES use-cases. The equipment, which is developed in the framework of the 5G-ROUTES project, is discussed further in the deliverable. Please refer to D2.1 for more details on how the different use-cases fit in the project architecture.

Table 3. Equipment used in the 5G-ROUTES use-cases

Use Case	Vehicle	OBU	Other devices	Servers
1.1 Dynamic vehicles platooning	EDI, LMT	EDI OBU (with lidar, radar, GNSS)		MQTT broker
1.2 Cooperative lane change	EDI, LMT	EDI OBU (with lidar, radar, GNSS)	Obstacle	MQTT broker
1.3 See through view for safe automated overtake	VTT, EDI	VTT OBU (2x, 1 with camera)		
2.1 Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control	EDI, LMT	integrated	Traffic light controller, Cameras, RSU, Swarm Analytic sensors, 5G Router, Traffic lights, Safe light system	ICS (Intersection controller)
2.2 Traffic jam chauffeur	EDI, LMT	EDI OBU (with lidar, radar, GNSS, camera)	VRU	MQTT broker
3.1 Sensor info sharing	VTT, EDI	VTT OBU (2x, 1 with camera & LIDAR)		
3.2 Connected maintenance	TTU, EDI	OBD-reader	IoT	cloud server
3.3 VRU collision avoidance	VEDECOM	VEDECOM OBU	VRU devices	MQTT broker
4.1 360o immersive multi-user gaming on the go	-		User smart device	Real-time game backend
4.2 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the go	-		5G smartphone, Laptop, Head Mounted Display, Broadcast virtual set, graphics station	-
5.1 Goods tracking visibility in multimodal cross-border logistics	TBD	Vedia OBU	RSU	IoT devices, backend
5.2 5G-based Proactive and Multimodal Management of Passengers and Freight	TBD	Wings OBU	smartphone, IoT sensors, infrastructure sensors,	cloud server
5.3 Continuous railway infrastructure monitoring with optical sensors	DR1 diesel train	PV OBU (with depth camera, LIDAR)		backend, train equipment

2.4 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The following chapters are structured as follows:

- Chapter 3 reports on VNFs, CAM services and V2V/V2X networks in a 5G context and shows how they are related to the use-cases described in D3.3.
- Chapter 4 details existing road infrastructure such as intelligent light systems and AI-based solutions for safer traffic control.
- Chapters 5, 6 and 7 detail the available infrastructure of the different 5G-ROUTES stakeholders for vehicle, railway, and maritime use-cases respectively. They also include details on available hardware, software, planned tests and required changes in existing systems to implement the use-cases.
- Chapter 8 concludes the report.
- Chapter 9 lists used references.

3 Network Connectivity

This chapter reports on VNFs, CAM services and V2V/V2X networks in a 5G context and shows how they are meaningful for the use-cases described in D3.3.

3.1 Relation to Use-Cases

In 5G there are two ways of communication between UEs: Direct communication using PC5 (Sidelink) or communication using the cellular network (Uu protocol). Communication using the Uu protocol will be the focus in **all the use-cases**, and PC5 will be researched as an alternative to Uu communications, mainly in use-case categories that make use of URLLC. These categories are:

- Automated cooperative driving
- Awareness driving
- Sensing driving

5G networks come with new architectural components, such as MEC, which allows functionalities to be deployed as Virtual Network Functions, either at the edge or near to the core. Almost all use cases will make use of one or more VNFs. Section 3.2 gives an overview of the CAM services which will be implemented as VNFs, and will provide insight on how the use-case-specific CAM services will leverage Edge Enablers offered by the 5G-ROUTES platform. The 5G-ROUTES platform and the enablers are described in more detail in WP2 deliverables D2.1, D2.3, D2.5, D2.7 and D2.9.

3.2 Virtual Network Functions (VNFs)

Connected transport-related devices such as OBUs, RSUs, smart traffic lights, environment perception sensors, etc. can produce large amount of data especially in dense urban areas and in intersections dealing with high vehicle and VRU traffic. The volume of distributed information will significantly increase as more and more traffic participants cross the barrier to the “connected” world. More information means ultimately better awareness of the surroundings, but also brings in challenges about the availability of adequate resources that are capable to manage this. Although each of the participating actors may very well implement internally, services and applications that explore all self-produced and received data coming from different technologies like ITS-G5, C-V2X direct, or network based (provided that related necessary hardware and software stack is installed), computational processing power, storage and network limits can make such a task extremely difficult to achieve. In 5G-ROUTES, CAM services can be implemented at the Edge on a MEC node and eventually realized as virtual network functions that share common NFVI resources, and from which all interested actors can benefit from (Figure 1). 5G characteristic advances in network slicing and QoS guarantees can adequately facilitate the implementation of services with different demands and requirements, from safety critical (e.g., VRU collision warning) to plain advisory applications (e.g., Hazardous Location Notification). Especially in the case of safety critical applications the placement of the transport safety related services at the Edge of the network, nearby the area of interest and supporting a somehow “local” decision making, will enhance latency related performance, compared with conventional public cellular networks, which is of great importance in time critical dangerous situations. Moving service workload away from the core network towards the edge, leads to mobility applications with improved response times increasing safety and the general user experience.

In cross-border situations, such as in the Valka-Valga (Latvian and Estonian border) pilot site of 5G-ROUTES, handover issues between different MNOs from different countries are expected to occur and must be dealt with in a way that ensures minimal conceived service interruption (if any) from the user perspective.

The 5G-ROUTES Platform is a system built as a combination of innovative technological Enablers developed within the project to comply with different CAM use-cases' needs. Therefore, Enablers are to be understood in this project as pieces of software that facilitate an enhancement or new functionality within a 5G infrastructure. Each Enabler will offer and/or produce services from the 5G-ROUTES Platform to the UC Services. The 5G-ROUTES Platform, which is described in more detail in D2.1 and D2.9, will be deployed at each of the 5G-ROUTES trial sites and interconnected through a cross-domain bridging configuration of the Integration Fabric MQTT Broker enabler. The 5G-ROUTES Platform is a collection of VNFs (Enablers) that are deployed in the infrastructure before any use case becomes active.

Figure 1. 5G-ROUTES Platform overview

In 5G-ROUTES CAM services will be implemented as VNFs or VNF chains at the Edge and/or Core network. The complete list of VNFs including Enablers from the 5G-ROUTES Platform (both Core and Edge Enablers are described in more detail in D2.9) and the CAM Services from UCs can be categorized as follows:

- **Core Enablers:** these are involved in the instantiation procedure of a UC CAM Service, but do generally not have direct interaction to the UE or UC CAM Services after activation. The Tenant Web Portal is part of this group of Enablers and will allow UCs to interact with the 5G-ROUTES Platform and the underlying 5G infrastructure.
- **Edge Enablers** are deployed and prepared for UC CAM Services and possibly UE, to interact with them at any time. They offer a CAM-specific functionality in the cross-border experiment, which may be leveraged by multiple use cases. The current list of Enablers that will offer functionalities to one or more UCs include:
 - 5G network-based positioning and 5G integrated hybrid positioning
 - Assisted handover in cross borders
 - Low-latency cross-border synchronisation mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery
 - V2X routing using MEC
 - 5G localization for VRU protection
- **CAM Services** are VNFs that are required to be deployed before use case activation and can be decommissioned if the use case shuts down. They are deployed through the 5G-ROUTES Platform through the Tenant Web Portal and the CAM Repository enabler. CAM Services offer UC-specific vertical functionalities that will be used by the UE during the execution of an experiment.

The preliminary list of CAM Services implemented as VNFs related to the use cases is shown in

Table 4. CAM Services are closely linked to the technological Enablers developed in WP2. Refer to D2.1 and D2.9 for more information about the relation between Enablers and use-cases.

Table 4. CAM Services implemented as VNFs

Use-Case	CAM Service	Beneficiary Traffic Participant	VNF location	Responsible partner
UC1.3	Video streaming server	Vehicles	Edge network	VTT
UC2.1	Traffic Light Forecast/ Traffic Light assistant (GLOSA)	Vehicles	Edge or core network	SWARCO
UC2.1	Imminent Signal Violation warning	Vehicles, VRU	Edge network	SWARCO
UC2.1	Smart Crossing (Safe light)	VRUs (pedestrians), vehicles	Edge network	SWARCO
UC2.1	Multimodal monitoring	VRUs (pedestrians), vehicles	Edge network	SWARCO
UC4.1	Real-time game backend	Game users	Edge or core	Brainstorm

The CAM Services include:

- **Video streaming server:** service for enabling low-latency video transfer between vehicles. This service is used in UC1.3 (See through view for safe automated overtake). The service is described in more detail in D2.1.
- **Traffic Light Forecast/Traffic Light Assistant:** this service, used in UC2.1, provides custom assistance for the crossing of signalised intersections helping the drivers comfort and improving the environment quality through broadcasting information about the current status of the traffic light and about the phase change.
- **Imminent Signal Violation Warning:** this service, used in UC2.1, implies the usage of V2X technologies for the broadcasting of safety messages in case of Red-Light Violation of another vehicle or pedestrian.
- **Smart crossing,** used in UC2.1, implies the directing of a red-light beam onto the pavement reflecting the red traffic light, depending on the position of the pedestrian, on the display of the smartphone, by bringing a major contribution to pedestrian safety in the case when the view on the smartphone diverts attention from the traffic light.
- **Multi-modal monitoring:** this service, used in UC2.1, implies the deployment of sensing features based on AI and Video Analytics at intersection level.
- **Real-time game backend:** this service, used in UC4.1, is deployed at the edge or the core, and is in charge of receiving all users interaction, calculating the status and all the dynamics of the game and finally updating all remote devices accordingly.

3.3 Car Communications

3.3.1 3GPP Sidelink Communication Evolution

Figure 2 shows the evolution of sidelink communication over various 3GPP releases. The 3GPP proposed proximity services (ProSe), initially in Releases 12 and 13, to enable D2D communication over a new interface called sidelink PC5. Later in Releases 14 and 15 additional enhancements were proposed, primarily for V2X communication, while Release 16 proposed new radio sidelink enhancements such as increased physical resources, feedback channel, etc. For communication using sidelink PC5 interface, mainly there are three steps, i.e., synchronization, direct discovery, and direct communication.

Figure 2. Evolution of Sidelink Communication

3.3.2 5G System Architectures for V2X and V2V

In release 16 [1] the NR sidelink resource allocation has two modes, contrary to the four modes of LTE. In mode 1 the base station allocates the resources for the sidelink devices, through the Uu interface. In mode 2 the allocation is determined by a user equipment. Figure 3 and Figure 4 [4] show the roaming system architecture for the Local breakout and Home routed scenarios. In local breakout scenario the traffic of the roaming UE doesn't need to go through the home network, but rather, it can be directly routed from the visited. On the other hand, in the Home routed scenario, the traffic must be routed within the home network [5]. The red rectangle highlights the sidelink part of the architecture.

Figure 3. V2X communication – System architecture for the local break out scenario [4]

Figure 4. V2X communication – System architecture for the Home routed scenario [4]

3.3.3 Prominent Chip Vendors

There are not many chip vendors available on the market enforcing V2V communication solutions. This is mainly due to the high technological requirements for the silicone die production as well as implications on IP management and usage. It is also incorporating additional automotive requirements such as AEC-Q100 compliance to ensure high reliability what is crucial for automotive sector.

Qualcomm Inc. is arguably the most crucial company leveraging new generation V2V technologies along with NR 5G. While 5G is a focus of the company, it also puts a stake to a new technology that can support future mobility.

The second most known chip vendor is *MediaTek*. They do not present a very detailed product roadmap for upcoming vehicular communication solutions, but it can be identified that *MediaTek* put their effort towards safety solution such as Emergency Call “eCall”, in-vehicle infotainment systems and ADAS leveraging chipsets. There is a general lack of information regarding product roadmap for 5G NR V2V communication.

Another company that could be attributed to a V2V solution chip vendor is *AutoTalks Ltd*, specialized in DSRC-V2V solutions based on 802.11p PHY and Wave / ETSI ITS-G5 standards. It also incorporates C-V2X which is based on direct sidelink communication such as PC5. *AutoTalks* is a fabless company which utilizes ST microelectronics semiconductor facilities and manufacturing processes. Currently the company portfolio has three main SOC products.

3.3.4 Chipsets Available for Car-to-Car Communication

One of the *Qualcomm*'s flagship products for vehicular communication is custom C-V2X solutions - Q9150 C-V2X ASIC, which utilizes 5.9GHz ITS spectrum along with cellular connectivity features. From the specification [11], this chip is compatible with 3GPP R14, however there is no evidence for NR support.

Qualcomm has also developed a platform for vehicular communication called “*Snapdragon Automotive 5G Platform*” which uses NR 5G. According to the specification, this platform complies 3GPP R15 and supports both standalone (SA) and non-standalone (NSA) modes of operation. The *Snapdragon Automotive 5G* platform is optimized to support concurrent multi-frequency, multi-constellation GNSS, including GPS, Galileo, Glonass, BDS and QZSS. It also supports sidelink communication such as PC5 with 20MHz bandwidth.

AutoTalks [13] has three main products in their portfolio: CREATON2, SECTION and PLUTON2. The last one is a RF transceiver which does not implement a MAC, but it can be used to leverage custom solutions for V2V

communication. The SECTION and CREATON2 are complete V2X solutions and have similar specifications except that CREATON2 has a powerful application CPU and in-car communication capabilities such as CAN bus. Although it is mentioned that these SOCs have sidelink PC5 capabilities, there is a lack of information about supporting all C-V2X features. All *AutoTalks* products have AEC Q-100 grade 2 compliance what makes them suitable to be integrated in auto grade solution.

3.3.5 Integrated Modules

Integrated modules typically have user-friendly interface, such as AT command interfaces, and they are generally more affordable. In addition, such modules do not require to sign any sort of NDA with the chipset manufacturer. The most known module suppliers are *Quectel* and *Simcom*, and there are newcomers to this market such as *Alps Alpine*.

From *Quectel's* webpage available information few products could be identified as NR V2V solution. All this solution is based on a Qualcomm chipset such as Q9150 C-V2X ASIC or Snapdragon Automotive 5G Platform". The most appropriate for project needs are C-V2X AG15, 5G & C-V2X AG55xQ Series. Sidelink link is supported by AG15 module, while AG55xQ is NR 5G module.

According *SimCom's* product roadmap, there are a few products that can enable NR 5G and side link capabilities, like the SIM8100. This module provides PC5 feature leverage interface for V2V, V2P, and V2I applications. Although this module doesn't have 5G capabilities and complies only with 3GPP Release 14 CV2X PC-5 mode, the SIM8200G has Multi-Band 5G NR capabilities.

Another company that claims to offer modules supporting C-V2X applications as well NR 5G is *Alps Alpine*. There is no information available at the moment, however from press release [15] it is known that the modules are all-in-one communication modules that support both 5G NR and sidelink communications. They also claim that these modules have 3GPP Release 15 compliance. Although their press release states that the company has started to ship this module, there is no information regarding end products this module will be used in, except *Alps Alpine's* evaluation kit. In press release there is no evidence that *Alps Alpine* uses chipsets available on the market, which leads to the conclusion that custom ASIC-based solutions could be core of the module.

Figure 5. SIMCOM and QUECTEL integrated modules.

Usually, integrated modules have different physical interfaces to the user, such as USB, UART, SDIO, I2C, I2S, SPI, GPIO etc., and SDKs that enable development. However, these modules are not final, and require R&D which includes PCB development as well as certification procedures. This may also require RF front-end development which is not straightforward and may require multiple iterations. Although module manufacturers could provide a reference design for a solution implementation, there is still big gap toward final products compliant with technical automotive and safety requirements.

3.3.6 M.2 Form Factor Modules

Another option to empower embedded systems with 5G network capabilities is to use ready M.2 form-factor modules. Some of these modules are available from *Quectel* and *SimCom* and utilize the above-mentioned integrated chipsets. Such an approach is the most appropriate for rapid system prototyping, since it only requires an embedded system equipped with desired connectors and drivers provided by the manufacturer. It is also cost efficient compared to OBUs, for example. Currently, few models were identified to be potentially used for use-case implementations, but their manufacturers do provide SDKs for customer solution implementations. The most of these modules could be connected to the host embedded system using USB 3.0 interface which puts certain boundaries to module bandwidth capabilities. Figure 6 shows SimCom's SIM8300G-M2 module and *Quectel*'s RM510Q module.

Figure 6. SIMCOM and QUECTEL M.2 modules [11][19][20]

The given modules do not support sidelink communication such as PC5. Instead, they support 5G NR 3GPP Release 15 both SA and NSA modes. The modules require network coverage, and by using a higher OSI model layer, direct communication between vehicles could be achieved. This is possible by utilizing built-in AT commands to setup a MQTT client. This approach was described in a previous section and MQTT communication was chosen as the main interface towards partners interoperability within the use-cases. The built-in MQTT functionality only leverages this approach, which will be also used to encapsulate ETSI ITS messages.

3.3.7 On Board Units for Car-to-Car Communication.

The top for the V2X communication solution hierarchy is held by On-Board Units (OBUs), which uses all previously described components to combine them into a ready-to-use COTS solution. There is a number of companies that provide OBUs along with RSUs, such as *Commsignia*, *Ficosa*, *Unex Ltd*, *Cohda Wireless* etc. Such solutions include all necessary interfaces to bootstrap V2X applications, and most often have reference applications which can be deployed easily. This makes OBUs suitable not only for experimenting purposes, but also for validating scenarios in realistic conditions. The OBUs might also have certifications and compliance with international standards, such as "Functional safety" ISO26262. OBUs available on the market have extensive features to enable V2X scenarios, and are mostly based on a heterogeneous approach, i.e., using conventional communication such as DSRC and sidelink PC5 along with LTE modem to fulfil redundancy and C-V2X requirements.

Figure 7. Cohda Wireless and Commsignia OBUs

From the technical sheets of different OBUs, it has been identified that most of the C-V2X solutions have compliance to a 3GPP Release 14. No evidence was found for OBUs available on the market supporting Release 15 or higher. This is related to the fact that, even if there are chipsets and modules compliant with Release 15, there still R&D and certification time involved, which delays the appearance of OBUs the market.

3.3.8 Conclusion for Solution Availability

Considering previously mentioned chipsets, integrated modules and OBUs, it can be concluded that 3GPP Release 16 solutions are still in extensive development process, and some of the modules may be available for purchase only in 2022. There is still no fixed timeline for a 3GPP Release 17 module/solution availability from manufacturers. This leads to the approach to use available modules of 3GPP releases 15 and 16, such as M.2 in the 5G-ROUTES project, with further system upgrade to an upcoming release. An upgrade to release 16 would enable improved 5G-based positioning, massive IoT and satellite access, which several use-cases would benefit from (mainly in the categories of automated cooperated driving, sensing driving and multimodal services). The hardware that is available and currently worked with in automotive use-cases is described in section 5.2.

3.4 Planned Verification Tests

Initial verification tests should address the existing connectivity at all trial sites for setting up the reference and identifying pitfalls when deploying 5G network. Technically addressing coverage, signal quality, latency as well as uplink/downlink capacity of existing infrastructure. A particular gain from mapping the LTE connectivity would be for rail and ferry use cases as those not necessary bear high priority for MNOs from end user-customer perspective.

Table 5. Network connectivity verification tests

Test specification	Test description	Affected UCs
Verification tests of LTE (800MHz/ 1800MHz/ 2100MHz/2600MHz)	Existing frequency coverage. Existing signal quality KPIs. Latency/Uplink/Downlink speed tests.	All
Verification tests of 5G (3500MHz)	Deployed frequency coverage. 5G Signal quality KPIs. Latency/ Uplink/Downlink speed tests.	All
Verification tests of 5G enablers MEC/EDGE	R15/16 enabling feature functionality tests. Throughput tests. Transmission quality tests (TCP/UDP).	All

4 Road Infrastructure

Interoperability, “driver” warnings, and VRU notifications are becoming more relevant to the future of mobility. While the evolution of technologies currently based on 5G enables new capabilities for transportation, challenges are emerging when it comes to highly populated cross-border environments. A largely unsolved problem is the growing number of pedestrians distracted by their smartphones while walking on roads and intersections. Traffic management based on AI, enhanced road-side units, intelligent light systems, and 360o UHD elevated cameras with geolocation tagging are potential solutions to notify pedestrians.

4.1 Relation to Use-Cases

This section mainly considers use-cases dealing with the identification of different road-users such as VRUs to warn them from potential risks. One challenge for 5G networks is to add safety features to CAM Services in the context of a cross-border situation in which a reliable transference of information is needed.

UC2.1 Real-time traffic info and cooperative intersection collision control monitors road users while simultaneously exchanging road traffic data between VRUs, autonomous “drivers” and traffic management centres (TMC). Situational awareness is achieved considering collective perception messages (CPM) to distribute safety information between V2X-enabled vehicles. CPM considers the objects on the road not detected by the onboard sensors in the vehicles. The system uses the 5G network to transfer the gathered information (i.e., trajectories, routes, obstacles) from the enhanced real-traffic video towards roads users in vehicles or to distracted passengers or pedestrians that are using mobile phones. This is controlled via V2X communication standards. UC3.1 and UC3.3 include safety features for VRUs and vehicles considering the information gathered from the infrastructure.

UC3.1 Sensor Info Sharing deals with the sharing of observed data between connected road users. The road users, including vehicles and infrastructure, exchange metadata of detected objects using Cooperative Perception Messages (CPMs). This message format provides information on the road users detected (also used in UC2.1). Automated vehicles will take this information into account to avoid collisions with detected road users.

UC3.3 VRU Collision Avoidance aims to improve the safety of VRUs through the exchange of information regarding their presence. In this use case, the situation awareness level can be increased as different entities (vehicles, VRUs) share their location. In addition, vehicles and VRUs can benefit from objects detected by other vehicles and infrastructure sensors, thus extending perception with users that may not be connected or occluded at some point. Then, collision risk assessment and avoidance applications implemented in vehicles and VRU devices can rely on information provided by the smart infrastructure installed within UC 2.1.

Refer to Figure 8 for a visual overview of the described use-cases.

Applications for collision avoidance require a continuous update regarding the situation, i.e., location, speed, direction of travel of road users for a smooth anticipation of any risk and to avoid sudden emergency braking due to late detection. Thus, ensuring real time communication and network availability is required, especially in cross-border case. By supporting ultra-reliable and low latency communication and exchange of information between multiple sources (here, vehicles), roadside infrastructure and VRUs, 5G technology is expected to provide features to meet these requirements.

Figure 8. UC Synergies - UC2.1, UC 3.1 & UC3.3

The use cases belong to the Category 2: Awareness Driving, for which cross-border field trials are expected to take place on the A3/E264 motorway between the Estonian and Latvian borders. The municipalities of Valga and Valka are contributing with the execution of the extended trials giving access and authorizations to two intersections from both sides of the cross-border (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Locations of the intersections in Valka and Valga Cities

4.2 Architecture Overview

4.2.1 Valka Intersection

The city of Valka has proposed a right-angle signalized intersection with multiple traffic control devices. These are mostly traffic lights using fixed timing regulation, including pedestrian traffic lights. The plan view of the intersection (Figure 10) shows a geometric and symmetric design with enough space for vehicles to perform the required manoeuvres. The major road goes towards Valga city. There are two lanes in each direction. Figure 11 and Figure 12 present a closer look at the intersection, showing road signs and traffic lights.

Figure 10. Valka Intersection - Plan View

Figure 11. Intersection in Valka City

Figure 12. Valka Intersection and Details of the Traffic Lights

4.2.2 Valga Intersection

The intersection in Valga city requires the complete installation of all the equipment, the design, and traffic study due to is a unsignalized intersection. Due to the border crossing, bureaucratic aspects such as the electricity to power the equipment is being analysed. The following figures show a plan view and close-up of the T-type intersection. The available space allows drivers to perform manoeuvres in a safe way. The intersection presents pedestrian crossings due to a school in near to this location.

Figure 13. Valga Intersection - Plan View

Figure 14. Valga Intersection - Detail View 1

Figure 15. Valga Intersection - Detailed View 2

4.3 Description of the Equipment

The following table details equipment used in traffic-intersection use-cases, including the number of units in the different intersections.

Table 6. Traffic equipment overview

Equipment and model	Valga intersec.	Valka intersec.	Brief Description	Image
Traffic signal controller (ITC-3 Traffic Signal controller)	1	1	The main controller software consists of an ITC-Core, that handles hardware interfaces, safety features, and base algorithm. A range of software packages can connect through a fast binary interface internally and run traffic logic or supervise the operation. ¹	
Traffic Lights (Combia – CILANE)	6	0	The LED traffic signal CILANE is not only made of UV-stabilized polycarbonate but has also powder coated aluminium cover and rear panel. This combination of polycarbonate and aluminium gives this signal head an elegant, shapely design. Either the modern one-point or the classical two-point fixing are possible for CILANE. ²	
SafeLight System (Combia CILANE)	6	8	The view on the smartphone diverts attention from the traffic light. That's why SafeLigh directs a red light beam onto the pavement and reflects the red traffic light, depending on the position of the pedestrian, on the display of the smartphone. ³	

<p>Roadside Unit (Cohda MK5)</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>Built with the same chipset as the MK5 OBU, the MK5 Road-Side Unit (RSU) is a rugged outdoor unit with integrated dual antennas, housed in a weatherproof enclosure.⁴</p>	
<p>Swarm Analytic Sensors (Swarm Perception Box OP100)</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>Enables out-of-the-box deployments with pre-configured, edge computing hardware</p> <p>Includes LTE, WiFi, PoE Port</p> <p>Supports 1 to 3 RTSP based camera streams</p> <p>Best suitable for outdoor use⁵</p>	
<p>AI Cameras (DS-2CD2T46G2-2I/4I Hikvision)</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>High quality imaging with 4 MP resolution</p> <p>Excellent low-light performance with powered-by-DarkFighter technology</p> <p>Clear imaging against strong backlight due to 120 dB true WDR technology</p> <p>Efficient H.265+ compression technology</p> <p>Focus on human and vehicle targets classification based on Deep learning</p> <p>Water and dust resistant (IP67)⁶</p>	
<p>5G Router (XR80 Sierra Wireless)</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>With 5G connectivity, the AirLink XR80 offers 5G sub-6 GHz and LTE Cat-20 to provide high speed connectivity in 4G and 5G coverage. AirLink XR80 delivers best in-class performance and reliability, whilst ensuring continual operation even in harsh environments.⁷</p>	

4.4 Planned Verification Tests

The following table details the planned verification tests for road intersection scenarios. Please note that the timeline depends on the authorizations from the municipalities to perform the installation activities of the equipment on the selected intersections.

Table 7. Planned verification tests for UC2.1

	Description	Location	Milestone	Network	Challenges
Lab Test #1	Verification of Network and infrastructure	TTU 5G Testbeds (Tallinn)	Validate initial architecture / Ensure the communication between the systems	5G base station manufactured by Ericsson and commercially operated by TELIA (Estonia) and LMT (Latvia)	Service continuity considering the cross-border scenario
Lab Test #2	Transmission and receipt of C-ITS messages		Enable the cloud platform for data analysis and predictive algorithms.		Assure the transmission of data to test the predictive algorithms on the cloud platform
Lab Test #3	Data gathering and analysis		Final validation		Data analysis considering the continuity of the service in the cross-border
Localized Trial #1	Data Acquisition from the video monitoring system	Valga/Valka cities	Scenario trials / data reception and transmission Technical verification of the pilot		Technical verification of the C-ITS systems considering the video monitoring
Localized Trial #2	Aggregation of information and analysis		Enable safety features at intersection level (VRUs, vehicles) Functional verification		Assure the transmission of information between the center and the objects on the road
Extended trial #3	Final validation and analysis of information		Final Validation		

5 CAM Infrastructure in Vehicles

This section covers the architecture for both hardware, software, and car communication systems in the context of automotive use cases to provide a current overview for vehicles of EDI, VTT, VEDECOM, and LMT. Architecture improvements and modifications to fit use-case needs and achieve desired KPIs are also described here.

5.1 Relation to Use-Cases

This section details how the hardware and architecture specifications of the following sections relate to the automotive use-cases.

Table 8. Equipment needed for different automotive use-cases

Use-case	Leader and partners	Required in-vehicle infrastructure	Mode
UC1.1	EDI , LMT, TELIA, CTTC	Drive-by-wire system, RADAR, LIDAR, IMU, GPS RTK, network (5G) transmitter/receiver and HPC.	Road
UC1.2	EDI , LMT, TELIA, CTTC	Drive-by-wire system, RADAR, LIDAR, IMU, GPS RTK, network (5G) transmitter/receiver and HPC.	Road
UC1.3	VTT , EDI, LMT, TELIA, EEE	Drive-by-wire system, camera, IMU, GPS RTK, network (5G) transmitter/receiver and HPC.	Road
UC2.2	EDI , LMT, TELIA, CTTC	Drive-by-wire system, RADAR, LIDAR, IMU, GPS RTK, network (5G) transmitter/receiver and HPC.	Road
UC3.1	VTT , VED, EDI, LMT, TELIA, EEE	Drive-by-wire system, camera, LIDAR, IMU, GPS RTK, network (5G) transmitter/receiver and HPC.	Road
UC3.2	TTU , EDI, TELIA, ENIDE	OBU (by TTU), GPS, network (G5) transmitter/receiver.	Road
UC3.3	VED , CERTH, TTU, LMT, TELIA, EEE	LIDAR, GPS RTK/IMU, network (5G) transmitter/receiver.	Road
UC5.2	WINGS , CTTC	LIDAR, GPS, IMU, camera, Network (4G/5G) transmitter/receiver.	Road + Ferry (chapter 7)

Figure 16 provides an overview of common hardware components, which, used in different combinations by the involved partners, will play key roles in conducting the 5G-ROUTES use-cases. It includes several subsystems, such as perception subsystem, communication subsystem, power, and actuation subsystem.

Figure 16. Vehicle's general component overview

The sensor perception system includes all related environment data acquisition components and their interconnections. It includes a LIDAR sensor, RADAR, IMU, UHD CAMERA, GNSS RTK, etc. These sensors are primarily used for vehicle self-localization and path-planning, as well as perception of surrounding objects for behavioural planning and scenario execution. To implement these functions, the car is equipped with an HPCu, which is sufficiently fast for the number of operations that need to be performed.

The car communication system includes all components needed to achieve V2V-, V2I- and I2V-types of communication, which are core research areas in the context of the 5G-ROUTES project. Hardware includes OBU, NR D2D MODEM, PC5, and SATELITE connectivity, which is needed for automotive use-cases.

One of the crucial components of the system is the **DbW (Drive by Wire) unit**, whose main goal is to translate planning algorithm outputs to a real signal that is fed to the actuators (throttle, brake, and steering controls).

The last component is a **power distribution unit (PDU)** whose job is to power each component, including safety features such as current limitation, and to cut power in case of an emergency. This component must be powerful enough to power all systems at once, considering maximum power ratings.

These considerations were made by all automotive stakeholders to choose the best setup, which is described in section 5.2.

5.2 Architectures of the Vehicles

5.2.1 VTT Vehicle Architecture Overview and Specifications

VTT has a set of research prototype vehicles, which will be mainly used in 5G-ROUTES for the lab trials. VTT's research vehicle fleet includes the following vehicles:

- “Marilyn 2.0”: Citroen C4 which has been upgraded for automated driving, through computer-controlled actuators. The vehicles are equipped with a set of environmental sensors, and advanced communication equipment.

- “Martti”: Volkswagen Touareg (Figure 17), which has been upgraded for automated driving, through computer-controlled actuators. The vehicles are equipped with a set of environmental sensors including Intrinsic module for C-V2X and 5G modem for Uu connections.
- “eLvira”: Volkswagen eGolf, which has been upgraded for automated driving, through computer-controlled actuators. The vehicles are equipped with a set of environmental sensors.
- “Jarno”: connected KTM motorcycle, which is equipped with environmental sensors and with 5G equipment.

Figure 17. VTT research prototype vehicle Martti

The research vehicles are equipped with a set of environmental perception sensors, such as radar and laser scanners. Figure 18 shows the in-vehicle architecture of VTT’s research vehicles. The architecture is based on DDS (Data Distribution Service), through which the data of the sensors and the information received through 5G is made available to the other vehicle modules, such as trajectory planning and actuator activation.

Figure 18. VTT research vehicle internal architecture

Applications from other providers can be connected to the VTT vehicle, through common description of user data types in IDL (Interface Description Language). Below is as example the IDL for a trajectory, which is made available for e.g. visualization or for control of the vehicle from an external application in the vehicle.

```

module Path{

#pragma DCPS_DATA_TYPE "Path::leg"
#pragma DCPS_DATA_KEY "Path::leg pathId"

    struct Waypoint{
        short    number;
        double   lat;
        double   lon;
        double   vel;
        double   heading;
    };

    typedef sequence<Waypoint,1000> waypointSeq;

    struct leg{
        short pathId;
        short points;
        waypointSeq pathPoints;
    };
};

```

During the 5G-ROUTES the vehicle will be extended with a camera for low-latency video transmission in UC1.3. VTT will provide an OBU, which can be placed in other vehicles, which eases the need for integration and testing. The OBU does not have a connection to the vehicle, so is only useful for connected and not for automated driving. The OBU, which has been developed in the 5G-MOBIX project, consists of a laptop, 5G-modem, GNSS-receiver and antenna and power connection.

Figure 19. OBU from VTT, developed in 5G-MOBIX

The OBUs will be adapted towards the needs of the different use cases:

- for use case 1.3 (see-through), the OBU will use a camera for video capture, and another OBU will have display for showing the transmitted video.
- for use case 3.1 (sensor info sharing), the OBU will also include sensor, e.g., LIDAR or camera + radar and signal processing for detecting events.

5.2.2 EDI Vehicle Architecture Overview and Specification

In the 5G-ROUTES project there are partially used exploitation results of H2020 PRYSTINE and AUTODRIVE projects. A more complete overview of a current EDI car functional architecture is given in [2]. During the task 3.2 a new approach was identified and researched towards use case implementation. During this task EDI intends to switch to a solution using Autoware code base and deploy it in the vehicle. This approach will give an ability to retrieve parameters for KPIs assessment. Autoware is a package based on ROS which provides a comprehensive toolset for experimentation and data post-processing, for example, using pre-recorded experiment data in a Rosbag structure. The following diagram provides the Autoware software component overview and structure [3].

Figure 20. Autoware software component structure [3]

Currently the EDI vehicle contains 12 SEKONIX SD3323 cameras and 1 Velodyne HDL-32 LIDAR integrated on the vehicles roof platform, 5 ARS-408 Continental radars, custom made DbW system and Nvidia PX2 as HPC unit.

Figure 21. EDI vehicle component and sensor architecture

NVIDIA PX2 is a powerful system, however, it is putting certain limitations on use-case implementations. A crucial one is system availability and support, making this architecture unpracticable for deployment on other vehicles. Thus, the PX2 could be mainly used as a sensor concentrator rather than HPCu. For an HPCu, it will be more convenient to use an industrial PC with a powerful GPU, which will unify the architecture and solve software compatibility issues. During the task EDI will acquire, install and setup such HPCus to a primary and secondary EDI vehicle.

In the planned scenarios the following sensor data will be collected from every vehicle for data-exchange:

1. Speed (from wheel sensors and from positioning sensor data)
2. Positioning (longitude, latitude, altitude – from GPS, IMU, and lidar)
3. Surrounding vehicles and other objects on the road (from radars, cameras, lidars, etc.)
4. Static road maps (lanes, road signs – received from a central map database)

Sensor data collection modules as well as scenario application will work in Autoware/ROS ecosystem and will be propagated via ROS messages by a publisher/subscriber mechanism.

Sensor data collected by each vehicle software will be used locally by the vehicles and transferred to the other vehicles using the MQTT data exchange protocol and several binary ASN.1-encoded packet formats defined in the ETSI ITS-G5 dataset. These messages are:

1. Cooperative awareness messages (CAM)
2. Decentralized environment notification messages (DENM)
3. MAP extended messages (MAPEM)
4. Collective perception service (CPS) messages

The MQTT mechanism remains the same logically and independent from network technology used under it – 4G or 5G, regular internet server or mobile edge computing (MEC). The scenarios are started to develop using MQTT on a regular internet server allowing intermediate message latency and scenario operation in slow speeds at the beginning. Later, when more efficient network technologies are involved, latency will improve but scenarios will continue to work without any significant software adaptations.

To allow data exchange between ROS ecosystem and ITS-G5 binary ASN.1 encoded message types, we are developing ROS-ITS-bridge software module that provides efficient translation of packet types between ROS and ITS ASN.1 binary format in both directions.

Figure 22. Vehicle data exchange software architecture

5.2.3 VEDECOM Vehicle Architecture Overview and Specification

A modified Renault Scenic Vehicle will be used for 5G-ROUTES, which is a specific prototyping platform dedicated for various sensors testing. It is equipped and tuned particularly for perception test and validation in real conditions. The vehicle is equipped with various sensors (which are presented below), but this vehicle is not robotized. In fact, we have the ability in this prototyping platform to integrate and test new components easily and make all necessary adaptations before transferring the new developed technologies in our most developed autonomous platforms, when technologies are more mature and different phases of validation are finalized.

Table 9. VEDECOM vehicle technical information

Parameter	Description, units
Wheelbase	2702 mm
Front track	1545 mm
Weight	1362 to 1577 kg
Max Front Wheel Angle	65 ° Lock to Lock
Stopper Outer Wheel Bend	35 °
Stopper Inner wheel Turn	30 °
Wheel size	205/55 R17, R = 328.65 mm, Peri = 2065 mm
Reference Center	Rear axle center

Figure 23. VEDECOM vehicles LIDAR perception system FOV

The hardware architecture of the vehicle is presented below:

- 5 Lidars IBEO LUX (Figure 23), 1 fusion central, 1 synchronization central and dedicated Switch
- 1 VLP 360° laser
- A pair of stereo cameras in front: 2 blackfly cameras and one rear camera

- 4 radars Continental Short Range
- 2 radars Continental Long Range
- An Atlans Inertial Unit (IXBlue) coupled to RTK-GPS and a Peiseler Odometer
- 1 5G OBU for vehicular communications

Middleware architecture

As part of the 5G-ROUTES project, a portable connectivity solution will be integrated to the vehicle and necessary adaptations will be made in the vehicle architecture to take into consideration the new needs for identified use-cases. In fact, an interface will be developed between local vehicle perception and V2X information communicated to the vehicle.

A V2X Protocol stack, complying with ETSI C-ITS reference architecture (ETSI EN 302 665) is running on 5G OBU to support vehicular communications. In particular, the protocol stack implements different facilities services such as cooperative awareness, decentralized event notification, collective perception and can disseminate information using protocols such as MQTT.

Figure 24. VEDECOM OBU Architecture

5.2.4 LMT Vehicles

In the 5G-ROUTES project LMT will provide vehicles that will be adapted to meet the requirements of CAM applications. The first vehicle is a BMW i3 that will not be equipped with Drive by Wire functionality, because it will be used as the leading car, passing data to subsequent cars. The communication will be provided via V2V and V2I direct communication, as well as via the 5G network. Data-reading will be carried out via a connection to the OBD port, as well as parallel identification of the steering angle, acceleration and other parameters using a video stream analytics from front cameras. The other car, a Kia eSoul, will be adapted with Drive by Wire functionality and equipment for communication and environment perception, using the same hardware and software as the EDI vehicles. Considerations are being made to reduce the number of sensors, and to use alternative lidar sensors. An updated car architecture will be developed over the course of the project and detailed in the next deliverable.

5.3 Real-Time Latency of Used Messaging Systems

As elaborated in previous sections, different stakeholders use different types of messaging protocols for their vehicles such as ROS based messaging, DDS and MQTT. Hence, it is important to notice that these messaging protocols are operating at different abstraction levels. For instance, ROS and DDS messaging are mainly used for communication within given vehicles. Their main purpose is to connect different SW component in vehicles to enable autonomous driving. Such components are for instance are perception, control, trajectory planning, current position estimation, among others.

MQTT is proposed as middleware between different systems, to enable communication across the vehicles, as well as provide an interoperability interface. To enable interoperability, it is required to have standard payload for MQTT-protocol-based topics. ETSI has standardised V2X messages, such as DENM, CAM and CPM, which can be transmitted using MQTT between vehicles and infrastructure. This approach is widely used in other projects, such as C-MOBILE [22] and 5G-MOBIX [23].

To enable messaging using MQTT service it is required to parse initial ROS and DDS data to be interpreted as ETSI V2X messages with further encapsulation in MQTT topic. This will require to have a SW component in each vehicle performing such a procedure. This puts additional redundancy to the system in favour of interoperability. Several experiments were made to assess real-time performance of such approach what led to result which is sufficient to operate for autonomous driving use cases. Hence real-time is considered a latency as end-to-end delay measure for a message. According to the 5G Automotive Association (5GAA) white paper on requirements [21] service level latency for members of a vehicle platoon (UC1.1 in the context of 5G-ROUTES) should not exceed a range of 100-200 ms. By performing a lab experiment involving a MQTT broker in the network and a workstation running ROS, it was found that end-to-end latency is bouncing at the level of 10ms.

Figure 25. MQTT service

Figure 26. ROS-ITS-Bridge loopback test

The approach for measuring latency was following exactly method described above. The ROS position base topic were parsed and formed a CAM ITS payload which was encapsulated in the MQTT topic. The setup had an MQTT broker which interconnects two nodes, where first client was acting as sender and receiver, but second was acting as echo client. In such a way it was possible to time messages being send and received. By dividing total delay by two it is possible to estimate one way latency delay.

5.4 Planned Verification Tests

While working towards the trials in Valka/Valga, it is necessary to develop and test the different software and hardware components that enable key functionalities of the autonomous vehicles. These verification tests may range from local tests in virtual and lab environments to full-scale experiments on tracks to get as close as possible to realistic conditions. This section presents the planned actions by the partners actively involved in road vehicle trial implementations: VTT, VEDECOM and EDI.

5.4.1 Tests Planned by VTT

The following verification tests are planned by VTT.

Table 10. UC verification tests by VTT

Test specification	Trial description	Affected use-case(s)
Automated overtaking of connected vehicle capability	Test to be performed in test track on Pirkkala, first for static than for slow moving vehicle. Track latency and trajectory accuracy	1.3
Transmission and receipt of video. Verification of the OBUs.	Both transmitting and receiving OBUs in the same vehicle, test latency and service continuity. Test performed on public roads while driving	1.3
Integration of video transmission in VTT vehicle	Same test as above, but with VTT vehicle instead of separate OBU	1.3
Integration of overtaking request	Integration of the complete information chain for UC1.3 in the VTT vehicle	1.3
Cooperative object perception testing	OBU for UC3.1 installed on vehicle, CPM generated and visualized on another OBU, placed in the same vehicle.	3.1
Integration of CPM receipt in VTT automated vehicle	OBU for UC3.1 installed in vehicle or roadside, and data sent to VTT vehicle. VTT vehicle to perform action to avoid obstacle. This will be tested for static object on VTT premises and for slow moving objects in Pirkkala test track.	3.1

5.4.2 Tests Planned by VEDECOM

The following verification tests are planned by VEDECOM.

Table 11. UC verification tests by VEDECOM

Test specification	Trial description	Affected use-case(s)
Vehicle position and dynamics	OBU installed on vehicle and is able to generate CAM from vehicle data sources (GNSS, CAN)	3.3
Cooperative object perception testing	OBU installed on vehicle and is able to generate CAM from vehicle on-board Lidars	3.3, 3.1
Integration of CAM issued by VRU in VEDECOM vehicle	OBU installed in vehicle, and CPM sent from VRU VEDECOM vehicle. OBU is able to decode CAM and provide the information to supervision system for risk assessment	3.3
Integration of CPM receipt in VEDECOM vehicle	OBU installed in vehicle, and CPM sent from roadside or another vehicle to VEDECOM vehicle. OBU is able to decode CPM and provide the information to supervision system for risk assessment	3.3, 3.1, 2.1
VRU collision risk assessment	Upon the detection of VRU from any source (CAM, CPM), the system anticipates any collision risk with VRU and issues an appropriate message/instruction to avoid any accident.	3.3

5.4.3 Tests Planned by EDI

The following verification tests are planned by EDI.

Table 12. UC verification tests by EDI

Test specification	Test description	Affected use-case(s)
Radar integration	Read radar data from different positions on the vehicle.	1.1, 1.2, 2.2
Lidar self-localization accuracy	Drive on the Biķernieki track while executing Lidar-based self-localization. Compare positioning results with GPS RTK data.	1.1, 1.2, 2.2
Drive-by-wire system functionality	Test control signals generated by a simple program (e.g., acceleration and deceleration in a straight line).	1.1, 1.2, 2.2

Longitudinal (and lateral) control reliability	<p>Let the autonomous vehicle follow a virtual vehicle in a</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CARLA simulation 2. HiL environment <p>Let the autonomous vehicle follow a real car at low-medium speeds</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. around the EDI labs 2. on the Bikernieki track <p>Let two autonomous cars follow the leading vehicle to test whether any external factors influence the reliability of the sensors and software.</p>	1.1, 1.2, 2.2
Lane change signal acknowledgement	Let different connected units emit a signal upon receiving the lane change warning. Time and analyse signal under different conditions.	1.2
Perception system accuracy	Test the accuracy of the perception system for key traffic elements (pedestrians, crossings, other cars, traffic lights, lane markings).	2.2
End-to-end latency	5G message roundtrip test involving MQTT broker on edge, message format encapsulation/decapsulation, latency test with moving vehicle.	1.1, 1.2, 2.2

6 CAM Infrastructure in Railways

This section covers planned CAM infrastructure deployment for railway applications. Compared with other CAM scenarios of this project, the railways use infrastructure that is not shared, i.e., passenger and freight trains are operated only by licensed operators. This is significant difference between other scenarios where road and sea are shared by multiple parties. This situation limits experimentation and trial options as the railway infrastructure is an asset with multiple levels of security measures and regulation approvals that should be met prior to any experimentation. Since 1 January 2007, national and international freight transport has been entirely open to competition which means that that railway network operators are not the same legal entities that operate freight/passenger transport. This enables new business opportunities and cross border operations as well as new challenges. In this project railway use cases will focus on passenger services and infrastructure monitoring application scenarios. These two applications have several similarities/shared functionalities with on-road scenarios, as vehicle passengers might be using the same entertainment services as train passengers, and cars also scan their environment by means of multiple sensors. However mobile network infrastructure does not always provide sufficient coverage and network bandwidth along railways. In Latvia and Estonia railways pass through rural areas (deep countryside, forests, swamps, etc.) where it is not economically viable for mobile network operators to invest into coverage and overall service improvements. The chosen trial area fits this description as it combines cross-border train passthrough with a rural/forestry area with poor mobile network coverage and bandwidth.

6.1 Relation to Use-Cases

Modern railway infrastructure like any other complex mechanical system requires a day-to-day monitoring and maintenance. As the railway network is stretched across vast territories it requires fully automated or semi-automated technologies to capture, process, reason on, and store monitoring data for continuous (long term) infrastructure monitoring. Modern depth (3D) cameras in combination with lidar and other sensor technologies enable new application scenarios with positive potential business impact, in terms of cost-efficient railway network monitoring and predictive maintenance.

In **use case 5.3** it is planned to deploy a modern depth camera and lidar and other sensors on the train to collect and stream over 5G network sensor data for further data processing (refer to Table 13 for more details). Additionally, these sensors are flexible and will enable various data streaming scenarios at various bandwidths starting from few megabits per second to 50 Mbps. This setup will allow us to provide constant high volume data stream for 5G network performance stability while performing tests.

Another railway-relevant scenario enabled by 5G networks is “infotainment on the go”. For this, **use cases 4.1 and 4.2** let passengers use smartphones and VR helmets that would connect with these networks from any environment or means of transport (at home, walking, train, ferry, plane). Developed by Brainstorm, the focus is on providing infotainment to passengers in transports. Use case 4.1 is centered on a multi-player 360° augmented reality game, which requires complete synchronicity between all participants with very low latency (uRLLC) and use case 4.2 consists of a 3D real-time collaboration tool using VR, and streaming high resolution stereoscopic video, therefore requiring no such low latencies but very high bandwidths (eMBB).

In both use cases, 5G compatible mobile devices (at least 2 smartphones or tablets) will be required to access the infotainment environment. While for use case 4.1 the connection is straightforward (direct communication via 5G), use case 4.2 will require at least one laptop connected to a 5G modem.

Since the infrastructure is not limited to the interior of the train, the system will allow passengers to make uninterrupted use of the infotainment system while waiting for a train and sitting inside it, until they have reached their destination.

Table 13. Equipment needed for different railway use-cases

Use-case	Leader and partners	Required in-vehicle infrastructure and equipment
UC4.1	BRA, ADS, PV, ATOS, EVR, LMT, TELIA	5G-compatible smart devices (phone/tablet).
UC4.2	BRA, ADS, PV, ATOS, EVR, LMT, TELIA	5G modems OR 5G-compatible smart devices (phone/tablet to use as a modem), laptops, head-mounted displays.
UC5.3	PV, ADS, EVR, LMT, TELIA	Lidar, depth camera, temperature measurement units, IMU, GNSS RTK, network (5G) transmitter/receiver, Edge computing module, Edge-Cloud computing node (located on 5G base station) and HPC.

Figure 27 shows a high-level view of the architecture in use case 4.1. While each game session can be hold in a MEC server near the final users (due to URLCC requirements), game results, user data, another general session information will be stored remotely in an external game server.

Figure 27. Use Case 4.1 basic infrastructure

Figure 28 shows a high-level architecture of the use case 4.2, where a presenter is captured and sent to a streaming service to be delivered to all the users simultaneously. On the user side, the setup consists of a headset connected to a laptop which is connected to a 5G modem to provide compatibility with the VR device.

Figure 28. Use case 4.2 basic infrastructure

For use cases 4.1, 4.2 and 5.3, final trials are planned on the route from Valga railway station (Estonia) to Lugaži railway station (Latvia). The train will start its route in Estonia where sensors will stream their readings via Estonian mobile network and after border crossing the network provider will switch to LMT network. One of our objectives is to practically try out, evaluate, and choose the best suitable data processing method (Edge, Edge-Cloud or Cloud) for our desired application scenario.

6.2 Architecture Overview

The CAM infrastructure will be deployed on a diesel-electro inter-city passenger train. The train platform will be used to deploy a sensor kit, edge computing units and 5G modems, 360° Immersive multi-user gaming and 3D real-time virtual collaboration on the move will be executed on mobile devices carried by passengers. It is planned to deploy sensors on the front and rear side of the train (Figure 29), however, sensor location might be adjusted according to test results. Additionally, it is worth noting that the diesel-electro generator might have influence the 5G network performance as it may produce EM interference and noise. The extent to which the generator impacts 4G/5G network and other sensor performance, will be tested and documented.

Figure 29. Train schematic with component locations

Optical sensors generate a large volume of raw data, which is to be merged with data from a GNSS sensor and streamed over mobile network to the 5G-Core Edge Site for pre-processing. At this stage, data clean-up and transformations will be done to prepare for transfer to a Cloud server for further applications and storage. A complete data flow is provided in Figure 30.

Figure 30. Sensor data flow

Railway's network is stretched across vast territories, so it requires fully automated or semi-automated technologies to capture, process, reason on, and store monitoring data for cost efficient and continuous (long term) infrastructure monitoring. It is planned to use depth cameras and lidar to capture data about railway rail dimensions and other information that can be used for infrastructure monitoring (see Figure 31 for a depth measurement sample). The main objectives for setup are as follows:

- Develop and test a cost-effective and efficient railway infrastructure monitoring data collection process for further data processing, analysis, and application
- Evaluate lidar and depth camera sensor data quality for continuous railway infrastructure monitoring
- Evaluate a preventive maintenance approach and new a maintenance business model
- Predictive analytics - enable long-term effective maintenance and repair services

These objectives are to be met via collection and processing of optical sensor data at the Edge Site and Cloud server. The next step is to analyse data to identify sections in the railway infrastructure that require attention and maintenance. This could potentially lead to an increase in infrastructure quality and safety through automated long-term monitoring. The collected sensor data may additionally be used for automated or remotely controlled train application research and development. The planned setup will test cross-border relevance by practically testing and implementing the required monitoring capabilities between Estonia and Latvia railway infrastructure, 5G session and service continuity (SSC mode 3) in a cross-border situation where 5G NR SA network must ensures no loss of data and connectivity and service continuity when crossing border.

Figure 31. Depth camera frame example [24]

6.3 Verification tests

Verification tests for UC5.3 will be conducted as several smaller tests which will verify individual component performance, and several larger integration tests which will evaluate the overall system setup. In total there are 4 planned field tests and 2 large-scale trials.

Tests will start with **Test 1** – Depth camera and lidar performance evaluation on railway infrastructure monitoring with local data processing and storage. The planned location is the passenger train depo in Riga (Figure 32) and the surrounding territory. The main objective of this test is to integrate and test sensor kit deployment and construction elements, sensor performance and edge computing node performance.

Figure 32. Passenger train depo located in Riga

In **Test 2** – depth camera and lidar data streaming over 5G mobile network to cloud (organization data center) will be tested. In this test, a data streaming component will be added compared to Test 1. Test 2 will also include measurements around the diesel generator to identify any interference it may have with 5G communication. **Test 3** consists of depth camera and lidar data streaming over 5G network to edge-cloud computing node located in 5G base station for data storage, pre-processing and further processed data transfer over mobile network to cloud. **Test 4 (Full setup/ end-to-end)** performs depth camera and lidar data streaming over 5G network to edge-cloud computing node located in 5G base station, data processing on the edge-cloud node, data streaming to other users for visualization in 5G network.

Trials 1 and 2 are planned to take place on Estonian and Latvian border (Figure 33). These trials will incorporate lessons learned from the 4 tests. The train will depart from Valga station in Estonia, reach the border-crossing point and continue its way to Lugazi station in Latvia.

Figure 33. Test area near border

Table 14 provides a combined overview of verification tests performed for all railway-relevant use-cases, including uninterrupted passenger infotainment solutions and railway telemetry operations.

Table 14. UC verification tests for railway scenarios

Test specification	Test description	Affected use-case(s)
Full infotainment application compatibility in a realistic context	Check the indoor coverage inside the train and validate that latency and bandwidth requirements are met.	4.1, 4.2
Full infotainment functionality test	Run the infotainment software over the whole course of the train.	4.1, 4.2
Long period infotainment test	Carry out infotainment tests of a longer duration, starting in the surroundings of the station itself or in its vicinity.	4.1

Sensor data capturing and edge processing	Deploy sensors on various locations and positions on the train. Capture data and perform edge processing.	5.3
Sensor data streaming to edge-cloud and cloud	Install mobile network modem and perform data streaming to edge and cloud components. Verify streaming performance impact on data loss.	5.3
Sensor data cloud processing and interpretation	Perform sensor data processing and interpretation. Measure required computing resources per channel.	5.3
Test 5G modem performance next to train generator and impact on bandwidth, latency etc.	Verify 5G modem performance based on antenna location and proximity to large generator.	5.3
Vibration impact on sensor performance	Test vibration prevention dampers impact on sensor reading performance on various sampling rates and train speeds.	5.3

7 CAM Infrastructure in Maritime

7.1 Relation to Use-Cases

Use-case 5.1 will focus on freight logistics and how to ensure connectivity on international multimodal supply chains. In the use case 5.1 freight cargo IoT devices are used to test and monitor connectivity. Aim is to utilize devices, which will be attached to vehicles that drive to the vessel. During the cruise, the vessel test environment is used to enable connectivity for freight monitoring, where IoT devices will report status and location information to background systems, which could be logistic service provider control tower for example. I.e., an IoT device, which is attached to the vehicle is connected to the vessel’s local communication environment - available for vehicle and passenger decks – and connected to the on shore via satellite and 5G connections.

The test set-up is used to test and demonstrate freight transport continuous connectivity, which is one of key enablers for digitalization of logistics. Based on continuous connectivity logistics service providers and fleet management systems can follow and control supply chains and react to deviations, if needed. Especially in multimodal supply chains this kind of transparency and traceability has been a challenge. However, the demand for real-time monitoring has risen because of global growth in package deliveries and continuously tightening delivery schedules. It is also stated that in future supply chain reporting and monitoring will be much more vehicle based than back-end system based. As now the rule of thumb goes that 80% of the information comes from the back-end system and 20% from the on-board sensors, this might be vice versa in future.

Use-case 5.2 will focus on the retrieval of relevant data from the remote vehicle with on-board sensors and vehicle’s ECU. This will help for the vehicle driver to know the traffic before can load the cargo to the ferry. The figure below (Figure 34) shows the process of the loading cargo.

Figure 34. Illustration for cargo loading procedure

The following functionalities need to be tested:

- Real time analysis and prediction of border conditions on two sides of the borders. The outcome of this analysis is the generation of requests for network slice establishment on both PLMNs to support the means of border control.
- Establishment of appropriate network slices on both PLMNs for the communication between the means of border control (cameras, sensors etc.) and the Customs servers
- Possible migration of selected custom services from Cloud to MEC in case of special situations or emergencies
- Establishment of inter-PLMN Network slice for the communication between the two border Customs.

The workflow analysis of the events is shown in the following figure (Figure 35).

Figure 35. Flow analysis of events

The aim of the pilot is to test and analyse quality, availability and benefits of such a system compared to existing solutions. These tests are done from network and connectivity point of view, but also from logistics business case point of view. From the network point of view the focus is on connection measures such as latency, message processing time, reliability, while more transport and logistics aspects focus on coverage and quality of information (accuracy, delay, availability).

Regarding the use case 5.2 the requirements from the network will be to:

- Estimate the traffic capacity
- Differentiate service type based on the ongoing services (eMBB, uRLLC, mMTC)
- Generate network slice requests based on the actual and predicted cross-border vertical requirements
Network slice creation, deployment, and management
- Network slice negotiation between a) two neighbouring PLMNs, b) verticals and PLMNs

Use-cases 4.1 and 4.2 will also be performed on the ferry, as it is a suitable environment for “infotainment on the go”. The applications and developments to be tested on the ferry are identical to those that will be tested in the railway context (chapter 6), including the KPIs to be measured and the internal architecture proposed for the use cases. Therefore, all the considerations that are made in the case of the train apply equally to the ferry, the only differences being the presence of different network infrastructures with different properties.

Due to the different properties of the networks to be used, we expect different results in measured KPIs, compared to the railway trials. In fact, given the specific latency requirements in use case 4.1 and bandwidth in use case 4.2, once the definitive properties of the networks to be tested are known, the tests will be adjusted (e.g., dead reckoning for UC4.1 and video stream properties for UC4.2), and their suitability will be assessed.

7.2 Architecture Overview

Currently, the test vessel has 1Gbit radio-link connection to the shore and for passengers, there is a Wi-Fi connection available on the passenger decks and cafeterias, but typically on vehicle decks, the connectivity is limited. Shipping companies have invested in limited connectivity since it is an important part of the traveling experience and comfort. Improved connectivity would, however, be desired from 5G. On the ferry line between Finland and Estonia, the distance to the shore is always less than 50 kilometers, so the distance to the shore is much shorter than in open sea transportation. However, vessels are big systems, where decks and other objects do create blind spots between vessel and ground base station. Typically, this challenge is tackled with various antennas mounted on different sides of the vessel or by using gyrostabilized platforms.

The 5G-ROUTES project is collaborating with Eckerö Line. Their Finbo vessel is used as a test platform (see Figure 36). The aim is to enable better connectivity for passengers and on car decks by utilizing satellite communication and 5G core transmission for backbone load balancing and integrity. 5G base station test environment will be built on the vessel and it will be used to connect the vessel, passengers, and vehicles into the shore networks. I.e., the vessel is used to enable a local connectivity environment for passengers and vehicles and hence enable continuous connectivity to the backend systems.

Figure 36. Eckerö Line vessel Finbo [10]

The on-board test environment includes advanced antenna systems (AAS), which is connected to the ERS Baseband, which is further connected to the indoor radio unit (IRU) with fiber optical cables. The IRU is connected to the two radio DOTs with Cat 6 cables. The ERS Baseband is linked to the core network via existing radio link (see Figure 37). Between the vessel and on shore 700 MHz and 3,5 GHz frequency are used for communication. This system also includes GPS for synchronization. The ERS Baseband and IRU will be installed to the ferry server room and indoor DOT will be installed one deck lower to the passenger area. GPS, AAS and satellite antennas will be installed outside the ferry on deck 9.

Figure 37. Ferry network logical schema

For the satellite connection Airbus will provide backbone connectivity (see Figure 38) satellite radio and antenna (from tbd satellite service provider) that is connected to the base station particularly for serving IoT messaging throughout the journey.

Figure 38. Kymeta antenna architecture

This system enables pilots where, a test vehicle will connect to the vessel network, when entering to the vessel and gets cell ID information, which can be used to get ferry entry/exit event data/location information. During the cruise, the test vehicle provides the vessel location information for communication and status reporting. When the vessel approaches to the destination the test vehicle will roam to shore networks and gets updates both cell ID and GNSS information. On Estonian side in Muga harbour the test vehicle provides mMTC communication load over 3,5 GHz radio connection between the vehicle OBU and RTK-assistance service.

7.3 Planned Verification Tests

For **use case 5.1** the focus in ferry tests is to test and analyse the quality and coverage of communication solutions. Aim is to test different communication solutions and load balancing during the cruise between Finland and Estonia. These results are compared to status quo measurements. In these tests, the message structure nor the content of the message is not that relevant since the focus is on the coverage and quality. On vessel measurements will be done in several trials in line with the project communication architecture development, but also to notice variation for measurement environment.

Under the use case 5.1 mMTC testing will be done in port of Muga. Aim is to test capability of 5G networks for cargo IoT monitoring in logistics nodes (such as ports). Aim is to use 700 MHz + 3,5 GHz, and test IoT device with location information, which is done by utilizing RTK data. In addition, an Android mobile test application will be developed to enable mMTC testing, where each device (mobile phone) is monitored every 5 minutes, leading to 288 messages per day per device ($60/5 * 24 = 288$). Each of these devices will open and maintain 20 000 – 50 000 TCP data streams to Internet test servers and simulate then 20 000 + devices/terminals. These 20 000 devices would then generate 5.76 million messages per day, or 67 messages per second. On field tests will be supported and prepared with office and lab tests.

Given that the expected infrastructure on the ferry will be compatible with both **use case 4.1** and **use case 4.2**, it has been also proposed to carry out field tests in which both use cases will be analyzed in this environment and in the context of a long-term journey. How these tests will be performed and their suitability on each use case will be evaluated based on the networks capabilities (land radio connection and satellite), on the use case's requirements regarding bandwidth and latency and on the KPIS to be measured.

8 Conclusions

This deliverable serves as an important stepping-stone towards implementing the use-cases of the 5G-ROUTES project. This document shows different existing and planned solution architectures and proposes ways for interoperability between involved partners.

A significant part of the necessary hardware for trial execution is already available and being tested, especially in the context of road vehicle architecture, where a lot of previous experience can be leveraged for 5G-ROUTES use-cases. Although some hardware is still missing, like commercially available modems for R16 and R17, the proposed solutions involve an intermediate level for communication that can already be used with R15 modems (by using the MQTT protocol and ETSI ITS message encapsulation), while new releases can be adopted during the project. Road infrastructure planning and ongoing communication with the local authorities in Valka/Valga have led to a good understanding of the available traffic lights, roadside units and other sensors that are either available or still need to be integrated before the trials.

Some potential risks were identified in railway use-cases, where the presence of a diesel generator inside the train may cause interference with network communication devices. To address this issue, the involved partners plan to carry out the necessary measurements to verify the extent of interferences. Partners responsible for maritime use-cases also expect some challenges implementing a stable 5G connection due to possible blind spots created resulting from the size and shape of the ferry. This problem is expected to be solved via strategic placement of antennas and gyrostabilized platforms. In the road-vehicle context it was agreed that the connected car use-cases have very little to gain from information provided by satellites. Thus, satellites were removed from all use-cases except the ones concerning maritime vehicles.

Following the architectural findings and detected risks in this deliverable, the next step is to proceed with further development and verification of the different components of the road, railway and maritime infrastructures, before moving on to the trial deployments of WP4 for KPI validation. The result of these trials is expected to provide crucial feedback for technical improvements that will be documented in D3.4

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